

Electromagnetic Self-Energy and Lorentz Transformations

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It is known that the electromagnetic self-energy: $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E \, dv + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \int B \cdot B \, dv$, where E is the electric field and B , the magnetic, does not transform as the fourth component of a Lorentz 4-vector. We consider a point charge and show that $(0, \phi)$ rest frame transforms to (A, ϕ) , but that gradients of both ϕ and A contribute to force. In particular, there is a force linked to $v \times B$. Thus, v and not only gradient contributes to force. We show that one may use $\int \phi \, dq$ in the rest frame to calculate $\int F \cdot dr$. If functions in the moving frame are of the same form as in the rest frame, one may use these from the rest frame, which is the case for a point charge. This leads to self-energy in the moving frame being $\frac{1}{2} \int dv E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \int dv B \cdot B$. B is proportional to v and so one has a magnetic energy piece which does not appear in the rest frame as well as the usual $g(v)$ Lorentz transformation piece etc. Thus, self-energy is not the fourth component of a four-vector due extra forces (especially the magnetic one) leading to extra self-energy.

Rest Frame Self-Energy

Consider creating a charge distribution by bringing charge from infinite. We use (\prime) to denote the rest frame. One may use:

Gauss' law: $\text{Grad}' \cdot E' = \text{charge density}' / (4 \cdot 3.14 \epsilon_0)$ ((1)) and

self-energy = $\int \phi' \, dq'$ ((2))

Self-energy = $4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \int \phi' \, dV \, E_i'^2$ ((3)) where $dV = d^3x$

We introduce the factor of $\frac{1}{2}$ to avoid double counting. Then, integration by parts, together with ϕ' and E' both dropping to 0 at infinite yields:

Self-energy rest charges = $4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \int E' \cdot E' \, dv$ ((4)) where $E_i' = -\text{grad}' \phi'$

We note that this self-energy should be equivalent to $\int F \cdot dr$ for building the charge system. We also note that for a point charge:

$\phi' = 1 / (4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0) \cdot q / \sqrt{xx+yy+zz}$ ((5)) Here ϕ' represents the rest frame.

Moving Frame Self-Energy

We consider the case of a point charge and note that according to special relativity: $(0, q \phi)$ $\rightarrow (qA, q \phi)$ where ϕ' is the rest frame potential and qA , and ϕ the momentum and transformed energy:

$\Phi = g(v) \phi$ ((6a)) and $A = \frac{1}{c} g(v) v \phi$ e(i) ((6b)) We let v lie along the x axis.

and $x' = g(x-vt)$ $y' = y$, $z' = z$ ((6c))

Given that $q \text{ grad } \phi$ represents qE (and force) in the rest frame, we suggest that $q \text{ grad } \phi$ must at least be part of force in the moving frame. The problem with $E = - \text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame is that E is a measurable and so should be proportional to a position vector (in the moving frame).

$-\text{grad } \phi = -\text{grad } g(v) / \sqrt{g(x-vt)}$ $= -g \{ g(x-vt) e_i + y e_j + z e_k \} / (g(x-vt))^{1.5}$ ((7))

e_i = unit vector in x direction, e_j in the y direction and e_k in the z direction

As mentioned in previous notes $\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial converts the $g(x-vt)$ dependence to: $(x-vt)$. Overall there is still a $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but that is fine.

We note that $\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial is linked to dA/dx and that A contains ϕ so $d/dx \phi$ should be linked to force. As noted in previous notes, this is not the only gradient of A linked to force. One may create:

$B = \text{grad } x A$ and then define $F = q v \times B$, where v is the velocity of a test charge ((8))

Thus. qE is not the full force, rather $q(-\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial}) + q v \times (\text{grad } x A)$ ((9)) is.

We note that the full force is needed to compute self-energy: $\int F \cdot dr$, i.e. to assemble the charges (which are seen as moving).

If one examines the form of $-\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial}$, it is of the same form as in the rest frame, except that $x-vt$ appears and the variable pertains to the moving frame.

Note: E is not $-\text{grad}$ of a scalar function.

$-\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial} = \{-\text{grad } \phi + vv \frac{dx \phi}{dx} e_i\}$ where e_i is the unit vector in the x direction.

Explicitly one has for E for a point charge that is moving:

$E = g(v) (x/r^3, y/r^3, z/r^3)$ with $dr = (dx, dy, dz)$ moving frame variables

This is exactly of the same functional form as in the rest frame. $\text{Work} = \int F \cdot dr$, but one may break it into two pieces, one for the electrical field and the other, for the magnetic. Thus:

Self-energy electrical = $.5 \int dv E \cdot E$ ((10))

If one explicitly examines B, one has: $B/(e_0 u_0) = 0 e_i - dz (g v \phi) e_j - dy (g v \phi) e_k$ ((11)) and

Magnetic force/q = $v \times B = e_0 u_0 \{ 0 e_i - g v v / (r r r) e_j - g v v z / (r r r) e_k \}$ ((12))

((12)) is again of the form of $g v v \{ \text{position vector} / (r r r) \}$ ((13))

where the x component is 0.

From the rest frame, one knows the value of the integral: $\int F \cdot dr$ for: $F = (x/r r r, y/r r r, z/r r r)$. One may consider each coordinate separately. Thus:

$\int v \times B \cdot dr = g v v \int y dy / r r r + z dz / r r r$ ((13))

The $y dy / r r r$ integral is equivalent to: $\int dv d\phi / dy d\phi / dy$ and $z dz / r r r$ to $\int dv d\phi / dz d\phi / dz$. Bringing in the $v v$, converts these to:

.5 $\int B \cdot B dv$ as one may see from the form of B given above.

The .5 is introduced to avoid double counting.

Thus:

$\int F \cdot dr = .5 e_0 \int dv E \cdot E + .5 / u_0 \int dv B \cdot B$ ((14))

One may note that the $E \cdot E$ integral is symmetric for $t=0$, but the magnetic one is skewed and so the energy in the moving frame is not the fourth component of a 4-vector. One may note that in the moving frame, one has the usual $-\text{grad } \phi$ piece, but also two new pieces contributing to force due to A, the momentum.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the self-energy of a charge density in the rest frame. We then apply this result to a point charge and note that even though we use $\text{self-energy} = \int dq \phi$, the result is equivalent to $\int F \cdot dr$. Thus, if one can calculate F in the moving frame (in terms of moving frame x, t), and F in the moving frame has a similar mathematical form as that in the rest frame, then one may use the integral results from the rest frame.

This occurs because we use a Lorentz transformation on $(0, q \phi)$ where ϕ is the rest frame electric potential. This yields $(qA, q\phi)$ where $A = v g(v) \phi e(i)$ (i.e. x direction) and $\phi = g(v) \phi$. One may note that: $x' = g(x-vt)$, $y' = y$ and $z' = z$. Using $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, one finds that: E (moving frame) = $g(v) \{ (x-vt)/r r r, y/r r, z/r r$. Here moving frame variables are used and $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. The components are of the same math form (for $t=0$) as in the

rest frame and so one expects that the electric self-energy in the moving frame is still $.5 \int dv E \cdot E$ (with all variables from the moving frame).

One may calculate $B = g(0, v d\phi/dz, -v d\phi/dy)$ and $F_{\text{magnetic}} = g(0, -vB_z, vB_y)$. One may factor out vv and find that two components (y, z) represent the math form of the rest frame. Thus, one knows that the integral $F \cdot dr$ is $vv (\int dv yy / (r^6) + zz / (r^6))$. This leads to $.5 \int dv B \cdot B$ being magnetic energy. One may see that the magnetic energy is skewed by vv . Thus, in the moving frame, one has a new force (magnetic field) linked to the gradient of ϕ , but weighted by v . As a result, there is no reason that self-energy should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector, given that there is an extra vv weighted derivative of ϕ * derivative ϕ extra energy piece. This piece arises because the "rest mass energy" piece ϕ is linked with force, but so is the momentum leading to two forces creating self energy in the moving frame.